

SUSTAINED LEARNING PRACTICES: E-LEARNING AND ITS IMPACT ON THE STUDENTS' SATISFACTION AND THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This study was conducted to study e-learning effects on the student's satisfaction and their academic performance. E-learning is contributing to sustainable education by minimizing resource use as well as supporting long-term learning adaptability. This study focused on key factors: course design, instructor quality, student expectations, prompt feedback, institutional support and technical assistance. This study was done by combining empirical and theoretical evidence from top academic databases to explore the factors influence the online learning experience. The findings of this study showed that, well-structured course design improves clarity, engagement, and learner autonomy. That will greatly boosts student satisfaction. The Instructor quality involves teaching ability, communication, digital skills, and institutional support in term of providing resources. Further, motivating students for online presence positively affects both satisfaction and performance. It is also important that access to internet and technology is also important to get the effective outcomes from the e-learning. Student expectations, prompt and helpful feedback are also important for greater satisfaction. This study highlighted that well defined instructional design, active involvement of teachers and responsive communication are required for effective online learning experiences. The factors in this study are supported by the Expectation-Confirmation Theory. This systematic review provides essential insights for institutes and policymakers those are actively involved for achieving quality education.

INTRODUCTION

The higher education institutions have adopted online learning as a core instructional mode. It's about flexibility, accessibility and possibilities to have more personalized study experiences. With pandemic, the shift to online learning was fast-tracked as universities went from physical teaching to virtual teaching. This change presented opportunities for creativity and challenges for teachers and pupils. It has thus become an important factor for explaining student

satisfaction and success in online learning environments to enhance teaching quality. E-learning providing students the freedom to learn anytime and anywhere. It's convenient as well as helps the environment by reducing the travel, paper, and energy need. Therefore, students can learn even during challenging times towards more sustainable future. By combining learning with eco-friendly practices, e-learning offers a smarter, more resilient approach to education in Pakistan.

Earlier studies are indicating that design of the course, prompt feedback, quality of instructor and expectations of learners have a significant impact on e-learning (Lee, 2014; Rajabalee & Santally, 2020). Here are the conditions which could be used to assess successful engaging students confidence in allowing them achieve their objectives. The studies are also indicating the confirmation about importance of variables previously mentioned. This paper, thus, intends to explore the effects of course design quality, timely feedback provision, faculty quality, technical resources and access to learning resources as well as learner expectations on student satisfaction and academic performance in online learning. The aim is to introduce a viable frame for online and hybrid teaching in the context of higher education institutes in Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

Now a days E-learning has gained attention as a flexible and technology-driven learning approach (Salloum & Shaalan, 2018). The instructional systems using online teaching use information and communication technologies to deliver, manage, and support learning activities for effectiveness (Moore et al., 2011). Furthermore, E-learning offers opportunities for continuous learning, unlike traditional classroom settings. However, its effectiveness is assessed through student satisfaction and academic performance.

Literature shows that online teaching improves student performance as well as also encourages sustainable learning practices, by reducing the reliance on physical materials and travel (Alam et al., 2021). Previous research comparing traditional, online, and hybrid instruction has produced mixed results regarding student outcomes (Lockman & Schirmer, 2020; Pei & Wu, 2019; González-Gómez et al., 2016). Some studies showed that students perform better in online learning environments when courses are well structured and supported. Others point out challenges related to teaching transitions (Henriksen et al., 2020).

The Instructor quality includes competence, teaching skills, experience, and the ability to understand students' learning needs (Luekens et

al., 2004). In the online environments Instructor plays a vital role in shaping students' learning experiences and emotional engagement. The instructors with quality skills improve student satisfaction by providing clear explanations, interactive sessions, and supportive communication (Munteanu et al., 2010; Arambewela & Hall, 2009; Ramsden, 1991). Students tend to perform better and show higher motivation when teachers facilitate online learning effectively, (Ladyshewsky, 2013). Recent studies reaffirm that instructor presence and responsiveness are among the strongest factors affecting online learning satisfaction (Shabbir et al., 2025; Chen & Huang, 2024).

The curriculum organization, instructions, learning activities, and assessment are included in course design includes elements (Wright, 2003). According to Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, a well-designed online courses enhance student satisfaction by promoting clarity and meaningful engagement. An effective course structure strengthens learners' knowledge and skills, ultimately contributing to improved performance (Khan & Yildiz, 2020; Mohammed et al., 2020). However, a course which is planned poorly, its content can hinder interaction with e-learning platforms and have negative impact on student satisfaction (Almaiah & Almulhem, 2018). Further studies also indicate that systematic, interactive, and learner-centered course design has a significant increase student satisfaction (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2014). Additionally, studies confirm that course structure remains one of the strongest predictors of online learning satisfaction (Kim & Park, 2024; Zhao et al., 2025).

Prompt feedback, according to Kinicki et al. (2004), is when students are informed about their performance in a timely way. Effective feedback enables tracking student progress, finding gaps, and improving learning tactics. According to Christensen (2014), there is a favorable correlation between performance and feedback. He said that constructive criticism boosts confidence and engagement. Further study indicates that by helping students and improving their academic performance, feedback can raise student happiness (Chang, 2011; Grebennikov &

Shah, 2013; Simsek et al., 2017; Brownlee et al., 2009). Further empirical study indicates that timely feedback has a substantial impact on students' happiness in online learning settings (Ahmad & Malik, 2023).

Student expectations refer to learners' beliefs about what they should gain from their educational experience (Appleton-Knapp & Krentler, 2006). When these expectations are met, students experience higher levels of satisfaction and motivation to learn (Bates & Kaye, 2014). Expectations align with performance in online learning. Meeting students' expectations regarding course structure, support, and interactivity significantly boosts overall satisfaction (Hew et al., 2024).

Students' academic success in online learning settings has been closely associated with digital literacy, which is widely defined as the ability to use digital tools for learning. Digital literacy was found to be a significant positive predictor of academic achievement in a recent study involving 894 college students. Additionally, this relationship was mediated by processes like learning adaptation and online self-regulated learning (i.e., students' ability to regulate their own learning in digital contexts) (Zakir, Hoque & Susanto et al., 2025). These results highlight the fact that digital literacy not only makes materials more accessible, but also gives students the ability to adjust to online learning settings and strategically manage their learning, which improves performance.

Technical assistance, digital literacy instruction, reliable internet or device access, and advice on using digital platforms are all essential institutional support services. The complexity of digital literacies is growing, and institutions must address several domains (information literacy, media literacy, digital citizenship, content creation, and data management) to prepare students for success, according to a 2025 systematic review on digital literacy in higher education (Technology, Knowledge and Learning Review, 2025). Students are more likely to successfully utilize available resources and maintain engagement when institutions offer structured support (orientation sessions, digital-

competence training, accessible resource platforms). On the other hand, the advantages of online learning are typically diminished or unequally distributed in settings that lack these resources or have unequal access.

Student satisfaction is an important predictor of academic performance. Zeithaml (1988) and Kotler and Clarke (1986) defined satisfaction as a psychological response based on perceived performance and the fulfillment of expectations. In online learning contexts, satisfaction is influenced by positive interactions, clear teaching methods, and accessible course materials (Malik et al., 2010; Martínez-Argüelles et al., 2016). Higher satisfaction often leads to better motivation, engagement, and academic success (Biner et al., 1996). According to Mensink and King (2020), performance reflects the outcome of combined student and teacher efforts and shows learners' involvement and interest.

The framework is supported by Expectation Confirmation Theory. This theory suggests that students enroll in courses with specific expectations. They compare instructor quality, course design, and feedback with these expectations. When their experiences meet their expectations, they show higher satisfaction and perform accordingly.

3. Methodology

In this study existing knowledge on e-learning students' satisfaction and academic performance was gathered to review relationship between factors affecting e-learning and student satisfaction and performance. The objective of study is to study and combine previous research, therefore, structured literature review approach was used. The five main stages was included during study: review design, search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, screening and selection, and data extraction and analysis.

4. Discussion

The study explored the main factors that affect student satisfaction and performance in online learning. While earlier discussions focused mostly on transitions caused by the pandemic, this study takes a broader approach. It aims to understand

how teaching methods and design elements impact learners' experiences in a virtual setting.

The findings showed that Course Design, Instructor Quality, Prompt Feedback, and Student Expectations, with Student Satisfaction. Additionally, Student Satisfaction was a strong predictor of their Performance. Among all the factors, Instructor Quality was the best predictor of Student Satisfaction. This highlights that the instructor is crucial in the learning process, even in online environments. Students respond positively when instructors are clear, engaging, knowledgeable, and responsive. These results confirm that instructors must have not only technical skills to manage online classes but also teaching and people skills to keep students motivated and understanding.

Course Design also had a significant positive effect on student satisfaction. When courses have a logical flow, relevant material, varied teaching resources, and clear learning goals, students find it easier to connect with the content. The findings support previous research that emphasizes the need for clear instructional design to achieve good learning outcomes. Similarly, Prompt Feedback significantly improved student satisfaction. Students appreciate quick responses from instructors as these reduce uncertainty, help them improve, and reinforce their learning. The study highlights that timely academic help is vital for a positive online learning experience.

Effective online learning is made possible by students' digital skills and digital access. Pupils who have access to dependable devices, the internet, and digital literacy participate more actively in class, use platforms more effectively, and perform better academically. The potential of online learning is constrained, and performance and satisfaction may suffer in the absence of adequate access or expertise. Student engagement and learning outcomes are directly impacted by the quality and accessibility of educational resources as well as institutional support. Students can practice skills, comprehend material, and solve technical or academic problems with the aid of well-designed digital resources and easily accessible support services. Inadequate resources or assistance can impede learning, lower motivation,

and have a detrimental impact on output and satisfaction.

Student Expectations also had a significant impact on satisfaction. When online teaching matches what students expect in terms of quality, support, and delivery, satisfaction increases. This stresses the need to set clear learning expectations and communicate course structures early in the semester. Finally, Student Satisfaction positively influenced Student Performance, showing that satisfaction acts as a motivator that improves learning outcomes. Overall, the findings support the conceptual framework and emphasize the key role of student satisfaction in shaping academic performance in e-learning environments.

5. Conclusion

The findings of study showed that a satisfactory performance of students in online learning context is significantly impacted by its satisfaction. E-learning is contributing to sustainable education by minimizing resource use as well as supporting long-term learning adaptability. Therefore, student expectations, prompt feedback, teacher quality, course design, digital skills, readily available learning resources, and institutional support must be available for improving the performance of students. Educational institutions must continue to focus on improving, these factors of online learning. The performance and satisfaction may be increased by strengthening course design, providing digital skills and assistance, fostering open lines of communication, and enhancing teacher training. The findings of this study offer important information for developing more effective e-learning systems as online and hybrid learning continue to expand. This study shows that students are well satisfied and performed better if it is well designed. It also supports towards sustainability by cutting down on resource use and encouraging flexibility. However, challenges like technology problems and less social interaction, but overall, e-learning is a practical and environmentally friendly way to keep education moving forward. By focusing on accessibility and engagement, it could become an even stronger model for sustainable learning.

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